

Electronic Supplementary Material (Online Resource 1)

Prospective life cycle assessment of circular energy-waste systems in university buildings: a scalable AI-enhanced workflow using openLCA and Brightway2

Table S-Glossary. Abbreviations and symbols

Term	Definition
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCI	Life Cycle Inventory
LCIA	Life Cycle Impact Assessment
pLCA	Prospective Life Cycle Assessment
CLCA	Consequential Life Cycle Assessment
EUI	Energy-use intensity ($\text{kWh}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{yr}^{-1}$)
MSW	Municipal solid waste
GWP100	Global warming potential, 100-year (IPCC 2013)
AusLCI	Australian Life Cycle Inventory database (v1.42)
GUI	Graphical user interface (unit factors in openLCA)
CRN	Common random numbers
SRC	Standardised Regression Coefficient
SRRC	Standardised Rank Regression Coefficient
E_{tot}	Annual electricity consumption ($\text{kWh}\cdot\text{yr}^{-1}$)
A	Floor area (m^2)

PV_kWp	Rooftop photovoltaic capacity (kWp)
PV_yield	PV yield (kWh·kWp ⁻¹ ·yr ⁻¹)
p_PV	On-site PV self-use fraction (–)
f_PV	PV self-use relative to E_tot (–)
d	Diversion rate (–)
W_tot	Total solid waste mass (kg·yr ⁻¹)
CF_grid	Grid electricity characterisation factor (kg CO ₂ -eq·kWh ⁻¹)
CF_PV	PV electricity characterisation factor (kg CO ₂ -eq·kWh ⁻¹)
CF_landfill	Landfill characterisation factor (kg CO ₂ -eq·kg ⁻¹)
CF_compost	Compost characterisation factor (kg CO ₂ -eq·kg ⁻¹)
k_grid	Alignment constant for consistency check (dimensionless)
FU	Functional unit
LV	Low voltage
IAM	Integrated assessment model

Table S0. Scenario matrix and headline takeaway

Grid × diversion used throughout. Takeaway: Swapping current → Queensland-2050 halves CF_grid and yields ≈ -47 % annual GWP; raising diversion from ≈ 64–66 % to 77 % changes totals by ≈ 5 t CO₂-eq·yr⁻¹ (marginal effect).

Scenario label	Grid mix	Diversion	What it represents
Current–64 %	Queensland current, LV	≈ 64–66 %	Baseline diversion under current grid
Current–77 %	Queensland current, LV	77 %	Improved diversion under current grid

QLD-2050–64 %	Queensland-2050 prospective mix	≈ 64–66 %	Baseline diversion under decarbonised grid
QLD-2050–77 %	Queensland-2050 prospective mix	77 %	Improved diversion under decarbonised grid

Table S1. Parameters, units, distributions and sources

“UQ internal” items are shown as ranges/distributions to protect confidentiality. Official AusLCI (v1.42; IPCC 2013 GWP100) values are used for reporting; starred entries (*) are used only for the consistency check to align the meta-model means to openLCA ($\pm 0.5\%$).

Parameter	Symbol	Unit	Distribution / Value	Centre / Bounds	Source / Notes
Energy-use intensity	EUI	kWh·m ⁻² ·yr ⁻¹	Lognormal	GM = 120; GSD = 1.10	UQ metered; used for E _{tot}
Floor area	A	m ²	Fixed	21,000	UQ building data
Annual electricity	E _{tot}	kWh·yr ⁻¹	Derived	E _{tot} = EUI × A ≈ 2.52 × 10 ⁶	Derived (21,000 × 120)
PV capacity	PV_kWp	kWp	Lognormal	GM = 95.75; GSD = 1.025	UQ system size
PV yield	PV_yield	kWh·kWp ⁻¹ ·yr ⁻¹	Triangular	1200 / 1350 / 1620	Brisbane solar resource
PV self-use	p_PV	–	Uniform	0.85–1.00	On-site use fraction
Grid factor (GUI)	CF_grid	kg CO ₂ -eq·kWh ⁻¹	Discrete	0.851 (current) / 0.445 (2050)	AusLCI v1.42; IPCC 2013
PV factor (variant)	CF_PV	kg CO ₂ -eq·kWh ⁻¹	Constant	0 (baseline) / 0.045 (PV-included)	IEA-PVPS ; NREL

Total waste	W_tot	kg·yr ⁻¹	Lognormal	GM = 50,000; GSD = 1.10	UQ waste audit
Diversion rate	d	–	Triangular	0.60/0.64/0.68 (64 %); 0.72/0.77/0.81 (77 %)	Two settings
Organics share	s_org	–	Triangular	0.50 / 0.60 / 0.70	Composition assumption
Landfill factor	CF_landfill	kg CO ₂ -eq·kg ⁻¹	Constant	0.833	AusLCI v1.42
Compost factor	CF_compost	kg CO ₂ -eq·kg ⁻¹	Derived	0.046 (= 0.00164 kg CH ₄ × 28)	IPCC 2013
Baseline materials	BASE	kg CO ₂ -eq·yr ⁻¹	Constant	0	Linked for audit, deactivated
Grid factor (aligned)*	CF_grid*	kg CO ₂ -eq·kWh ⁻¹	Constant	0.895 / 0.470	Consistency check only

Table S2. Unit factors and alignment values (reporting vs check-only)

Flow / factor	Symbol	Unit	GUI (reporting)	Meta-model alignment *	Used in reporting	Source
Electricity — QLD current LV	CF_grid (current)	kg CO ₂ -eq·kWh ⁻¹	0.851	0.895*	Yes	AusLCI v1.42; IPCC 2013
Electricity — QLD-2050	CF_grid (2050)	kg CO ₂ -eq·kWh ⁻¹	0.445	0.470*	Yes	AusLCI v1.42; IPCC 2013
MSW — landfill	CF_landfill	kg CO ₂ -eq·kg ⁻¹	0.833	—	Yes	AusLCI v1.42
Organics — compost	CF_compost	kg CO ₂ -eq·kg ⁻¹	0.046	—	Yes	IPCC 2013 (derived)
Rooftop PV — baseline	CF_PV	kg CO ₂ -eq·kWh ⁻¹	0	—	Yes (baseline)	Subtract-only
Rooftop	CF_PV	kg CO ₂ -eq·k	0.045	—	Yes	IEA-PVPS;

PV — included	(variant)	Wh ⁻¹			(side-by-side)	NREL
Organics — compost (sensitivity, CH ₄ GWP100=34)	CF_compост (sens.)	kg CO ₂ -eq·kg ⁻¹	—	—	No (Sensitivity only; value 0.056 = 0.00164 × 34)	IPCC 2013 (with climate-carbon feedback)

* Alignment values are used only for the consistency check to reproduce openLCA scenario means within ±0.5 %. All reported values use GUI factors.

Table S3. Monte Carlo and sampling settings (openLCA vs Brightway2)

Model	n (runs)	Seed	Sampling	Paired-contrast design	Notes
openLCA	2000 / scenario	—	Independent MC per scenario	—	Distributions as in Table S1
Brightway2 (Python)	3000 shared samples	SEED = 2025	CRN (common random numbers)	Paired scenarios share random stream; only target lever changes (e.g., d; or CF_grid for grid swap)	For check-only, CF_grid* aligns means; reported values use GUI factors

Parameter definitions appear in Table S1

Supplementary Figures (S4–S6)

* connected for auditing but deactivated in reported scenarios

Fig. S4 Foreground network for “AEB operation, 1 year” (openLCA)

Nodes show the three purchases to the foreground. The annualised materials link remains connected for auditing yet deactivated in reported scenarios. The figure documents the boundary and mapping used in openLCA

Fig. S5 GUI evidence—Queensland current LV electricity (AusLCI v1.42; IPCC 2013 GWP100)

The panel shows the dataset label and the unit factor used for reporting (0.851 kg CO₂-eq·kWh⁻¹). Purpose: traceability and auditability.

Fig. S6 GUI evidence—Queensland-2050 electricity mix (AusLCI v1.42; IPCC 2013 GWP100)

The panel shows the dataset label and the unit factor used for reporting (0.445 kg CO₂-eq·kWh⁻¹). Together with Fig. S5, it documents the specific electricity datasets applied.

Table S7. Consistency check — openLCA vs meta-model (means, kg CO₂-eq·yr⁻¹)

Scenario	openLCA mean	Meta-model mean	Δ (abs)	Δ (%)
Div64_Grid Current	2,151,000.000	2,158,339.465	7,339.465	0.341 %
Div64_Grid2050	1,136,000.000	1,140,971.020	4,971.020	0.438 %
Div77_Grid Current	2,151,000.000	2,153,237.016	2,237.016	0.104 %
Div77_Grid2050	1,133,000.000	1,135,868.571	2,868.571	0.253 %

All four meet ± 0.5 % alignment. GUI rounding can mask the small ≈ 5 t CO₂-eq·yr⁻¹ diversion effect. $k_{\text{grid,current}} = 0.895/0.851 = 1.051705$; $k_{\text{grid,2050}} = 0.470/0.445 = 1.056180$ (check-only).

Reproducibility and data availability

We version the openLCA project and AusLCI v1.42 datasets; exports include high-precision statistics (mean, σ , P5–P95). A minimal Python/Brightway2 package defaults to GUI unit factors and provides a switch to apply k_{grid} for the consistency check without affecting reported numbers. Screenshots of the foreground network and dataset panels are provided in Figs. S4–S6. Zenodo archiving will follow publication; see Data availability in the main text (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17236241).